

TECHNOLOGY OF BASIC PROCESSING OF SLOPED FIELDS AND GRAIN
PLANTING

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Abstract. The article presents a technology that implements the simultaneous sowing of spiked grain seeds at three different depths and the creation of ditches and scythes against water erosion on sloping fields.

Keywords: Slope fields, soil, erosion, main tillage, loosening, ditching, sickle formation, planting, grain, technology.

In our republic, in order to reduce the energy and labor consumption in agricultural production, to save resources, the use of advanced technologies in the cultivation of agricultural crops and the development of high-performance agricultural machines are being carried out on a large scale [1-4]. In particular, consistent reforms are being implemented in the use of resource-efficient technologies for protecting the soil from wind and water erosion, as well as the use of advanced methods of agrotechnology in increasing the productivity of grain crops.

In the cultivation of sloping land, it may not always be effective to stop water flow by loosening the soil and forming scythes in its lower part to prepare it for planting, planting and at the same time protecting it from water erosion. This condition is felt when the rain is in the form of a shower. To eliminate this, it is advisable to create a sickle on the surface of the softened soil. The mentioned disadvantages require the development of a new technology of minimum tillage in the cultivation of sloping land.

As a result of the analysis of the conducted research and scientific research [5-9], a new technology of cultivation and planting of sloping lands was developed. One of the unique features of this technology is the simultaneous planting of seeds and the formation of an irrigation ditch when preparing the soil for planting.

In the proposed technology, the following processes are performed in one pass (Fig. 1): loosening the soil alternately along the lines where seeds are planted and irrigation ditches are formed, forming sickle and irrigation ditches by overturning the soil slab, sowing seeds in strip form along the lines that are softened and where the sickle and irrigation ditch are formed. As a result, crops are planted on time and water runoff and water erosion are prevented.

1 – picture. Schematic of the new technological process of tillage and planting on sloping land: a – cross-section of the field after softening the soil along the sowing line; b - a

view of the cross section of the field after softening the soil along the lines where seeds are planted and irrigation ditches are formed; *v* – cross-sectional view of the initially formed ditch and scythe; *g* – cross-sectional view of fully formed ditch and scythe

The proposed technology is carried out in the following sequence: along the lines where the seeds are to be planted, the soil is gradually loosened at a depth of $a_y=22-25$ cm (Fig. 1, a); along the axis of symmetry of the seed to be planted and the irrigation ditch to be formed, the soil is gradually softened at a depth of $a_y=22-25$ cm (Fig. 1, b); along the axis of symmetry of the irrigation ditch, the softened row spacing plate is turned to the left, and an irrigation ditch and scythe in the form of a sinusoid with a depth of a_y are formed (Fig. 1, v); The crops are planted in ribbons along the lines softened and formed by a sickle and an irrigation ditch (Fig. 1, g).

Carrying out the above-mentioned operations in one go protects the soil moisture of the cultivated zone on the slope and its erosion and over-densification, drastically reduces the time of soil preparation for planting and planting, saves material and energy resources during soil cultivation, preparation for planting and planting, that is, the number of aggregates passes through the field 3- Due to reduction up to 4 times, minimum tillage is ensured.

The machine implementing this technology is equipped with a frame 1, capacity 2, planting devices 3, front softeners 4 and 6 equipped with flaps 5 and 7 located at a high and medium height relative to the blade of the softener blade, with flaps 5, 7 and 11 at a high, medium and low height the equipped second row consists of softeners 8, 10 and 9 and a scythe generator 12 (Fig. 2).

1 - frame; 2 – capacity; 3 - planting devices; 4, 6, 8, 9, 10 – softening paws; 5, 7, 11 – onions; 12 – scythe generators; 13 - knives

Figure 2. Construction scheme of tillage and grain planting machine.

Calculations carried out to determine the technical and economic indicators of a machine for cultivating sloping fields and sowing grain showed that when this machine is used for cultivating sloping fields and sowing grain, the direct costs of processing one hectare of land are reduced by 32.82 percent. It was determined that the annual economic effect of one car is 27684272.79 soums.

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